

On the Characteristics, Functions, and Learning Difficulties of Verb Complements in German and Arabic – A Contrastive, Valency-Oriented Study

1. On the Topic

This study addresses one of the essential issues in the field of contrastive verb valency. It examines verb complements in German and their equivalents in Arabic, specifies the distinctive features of each verb complement in detail, and contrasts these verb complements in both languages. The comparison of verb complement categories aims to reveal functional differences between German and Arabic. Given that structural discrepancies or divergences in verb complements often pose practical challenges for learners, this study seeks to provide solutions to help overcome these difficulties.

2. Research Questions

The present study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a difference between the definition, characteristics, and functions of verb complements in German and Arabic?
2. To what extent do verb complements in German differ from their equivalents in Arabic?
3. Are there difficulties in comparing the German complement categories with their Arabic equivalents?
4. What problems do verb complements present to students?
5. How can these problems be resolved?

3. Objective

The aim of this study is to directly deepen the syntactic and semantic knowledge in the area of verb grammar of both languages, facilitate the understanding of language, and offer practical benefits for teaching German and Arabic. Such a contrastive study is not only useful for advanced Arabic-speaking German students and native Arabic speakers but also for Arabic learners and German Arabists, as the German example sentences are translated into Arabic.

4. Research Methodology and Appropriate Linguistic Theory

Since this study is based on the principle of contrastivity and the concept of valency grammar, it relies on contrastive linguistics and valency theory.

4.1. Contrastive Linguistics Method

As the German language belongs to the Indo-European language family and Arabic to the Hamito-Semitic language family, there is significant divergence between German and Arabic, especially at the structural level. Due to these structural divergences, it is reasonable to apply the contrastive linguistics method in this study.

The purpose of contrastive linguistics is to identify the relationships of discrepancy, divergence, and equivalence between different languages. The concept of "equivalence," which holds great importance here, has been a topic of intensive discussion in linguistics and translation studies for decades. According to Schmitz/Kaukonen (2006), the term

"equivalence" is broadly defined as the relationship between designations for the same concept in different languages.

When comparing concepts and concept systems, the following equivalence phenomena may arise:

- a. Complete equivalence of concepts.
- b. Overlap (e.g., large/small).
- c. Inclusion.
- d. No equivalence of concepts (e.g., false friends).
- e. Terminological gaps (absence of a concept in one language).

The analysis of selected verbs and their equivalents already highlighted the need to examine the concept of equivalence more closely. In foreign language didactics, the hypothesis suggests that similarities between the mother tongue (L1) and the target language (L2) facilitate foreign language acquisition, while contrasts hinder it (cf. Michiels 1999: 5).

If this hypothesis is pursued further, one must assume that significant contrasts between the target and mother tongue lead to major difficulties, whereas minor differences cause fewer challenges. Thus, it can be stated: The learners' mother tongue systematically influences second language acquisition (Kleppin 2000: 31).

This study does not focus on analyzing learning difficulties or interference phenomena but rather concentrates primarily on the contrastive, valency-oriented analysis of verb complements in two typologically different languages. Contrastive studies are characterized by their primarily application-oriented approach. Consequently, this is also a contrastive, practice-oriented investigation. However, a prerequisite for any contrastive study is that the compared languages share a minimum degree of common features (Spreu/Sternemann 1983: 25). The discussions presented in this study will demonstrate that this condition is met.

4.2. Valency Theory

In linguistic works and common lexicons, valency is interpreted as the ability of verbs and other parts of speech to allow, require, or co-determine additional elements in their syntactic environment (Allerton 2006: 301f. /Ágel 2000: 15ff.). According to Askedal (2004: 80f.), the term is an allusion to chemical bonding; traditionally, Lucien Tesnière is considered its originator with his work *Éléments de syntaxe structurale*, first published in 1959 (Tesnière 1980). However, earlier studies also reveal ideas closely related to the concept of valency (Urešová 2011: 6).

Given that valency theory is frequently used as an application model, especially in contrastive grammar for foreign language teaching, this study is based on the principles of this theory, which form the core of dependency grammar. Dependency grammar, valency theory, and case theory play a significant role in teaching German as a foreign language (cf. Helbig 1988: 181f. / Welke 1988: 20).

The integrated valency concept, combining semantics and syntax, has gained increasing attention in foreign language teaching and has been incorporated into the scientific linguistic description of valency lexicons. This concept serves as the theoretical foundation for the contrastive comparison of both languages in this study.

The valency approach focuses on describing the morphosyntactic and semantic relationship between a verb and its complements or arguments. Based on the meaning of a word, it determines how many arguments (participants) are required by that word (cf. Duden

Grammar 2005: 396f.). There is "a fundamental relationship between the meaning of a word (verb) and its participants (slots)" (Bondzio 1971: 88). According to valency grammarians (Linke 2004: 94), "lexical elements – especially verbs – have the capacity to structure their syntactic and semantic environment by requiring a specific type and number of complements (actants) in complex syntactic constructions."

In the example sentence "*Die Universität gibt dem Professor einen Preis*", the verb *geben* as the valency carrier, and its Arabic equivalent *'a'tā*, semantically require three roles: agent + addressee + patient. In other words, the verb indicates that one person gives something to another person. Syntactically, the verb *geben* and its Arabic equivalent *'a'tā* require three slots or complements: subject + dative complement + accusative complement. The following diagram provides an overview:

German	Die Universität	gibt	Dem Professor	Einen Preis
Literal Translation	the university	gives	the professor/for the professor	a price
Arabic	Al-ğāmi'atu	tu'ṭi	l'ustāza / l-il 'ustāzi	Gāizah
Semantic Roles	Agent	Valency carrier	Addressee	Patient
Syntactic Roles	Nominative complement	Verb	Accusative complement/Prepositional complement with genitive marker	Accusative complement

The semantic interpretation in German and Arabic is identical, but the syntactic realization diverges significantly. While both languages exhibit semantic identity at the deep structure level, substantial grammatical differences emerge at the surface structure level. This demonstrates that the logical-semantic interpretation of events is cross-linguistic, whereas the syntactic realization is language-specific.

5. Verb Complements in Contrast with Arabic

In presenting verb complements in German, this study primarily relies on the "Valency Dictionary of German Verbs (VALBU)" (Schumacher/Kubczak/Schmidt/de Ruiter 2004) and its revised electronic version, E-VALBU (Kubczak: 2012), as the information provided in this dictionary about verb complements is both semantically and syntactically based. Additionally, the valency model of E-VALBU is characterized by its clarity and suitability for application to other world languages. In this study, expressions from E-VALBU, such as the term "Komplement" (complement) instead of "Ergänzung" (supplement), are used.

Regarding the components of the E-VALBU valency model, which consists of various elements (lemmatization, valency definition, complement classes, obligatory vs. optional complements, semantic roles, categorial specifications, reflexive verbs, pertinence elements, the impersonal obligatory "es," and the different passives), this study will only present those elements concerning verb complements.

In E-VALBU (2012), the sentence structure plan is "the set of all complement classes that can or must occur with a verb in a given meaning. The sentence structure plan is a valency frame with additional information about the optionality of individual complement classes. The optional complements are marked with round brackets" (<http://hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de/evalbu/Begrifflichkeiten/Satzbauplan.html>). Some complement classes are

further subdivided. Complement classes are consistently defined based on their anaphorization. In E-VALBU (2012), complements are categorized as follows:

5.1. Core Complements (Case Complements + Prepositional Complement)

5.1.1. Subject Complement (Ksub)

In E-VALBU, a subject complement is a sentence element in the nominative case that functions as the subject of the main verb. Although "es"-verbs do not have subject complements, they have what is called a "grammatical subject," namely the "es" (it). In a German declarative sentence, the position before the verb must always be filled, even if no specific meaning is assigned. Therefore, "es" is used. A subject complement can be questioned by "who?" or "what?" and can be anaphorized with someone/something or personal pronouns in the nominative case (er/sie/es), for example, "Ich halte seinen Vorschlag für sehr vernünftig" (I consider his suggestion to be very reasonable) or "Die neue Bluse steht dir gut" (The new blouse suits you well). In a sentence in the werden- or sein-passive, the subject complement of the active sentence is realized as a prepositional phrase with "von" + dative or "durch" + accusative. A subject complement sometimes appears as a subordinate clause. Sentence-like subject complements can be connected to a correlate if they follow the main clause, for example, "In diesem Jahr wird es von unserem Auto abhängen, ob wir mit der Konkurrenz mithalten können" (This year, it will depend on our car whether we can keep up with the competition). (<http://hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de/evalbu/Begrifflichkeiten/Subjektkomplement.html>).

In Arabic, there is the term *fā'il* ("subject"). This term refers to the function of nouns that are marked with the case "raf" (nominative). Subject complements are thus sentence constituents (nouns or personal pronouns) in the nominative case that fulfill the function of a subject in both verbal and nominal sentences (cf. Online Media World: 104 and 107). This function is of a grammatical nature. Semantically, a subject complement can have different roles, such as an Agent (a), a Patient (b), or another function (c), e.g.

(a) Arab. *yaḥmilu l-musāfiru ḥaqībatan kabīratan*
Literal: "The passenger carries a large suitcase".
English: "The passenger carries a large suitcase".

(b) Arab. *saqāṭat l-marwaḥatu*
Literal: "The fan has fallen".
English: "The fan has fallen".

(c) Arab. *tu ḡibunī ṣ-ṣūratu*
Literal: "The picture pleases me".
English: "The picture pleases me", where there is no Agent or Patient in the "picture".

All Arabic verbs require a nominative complement that corresponds to the subject. Under certain conditions, this subject does not need to be explicitly expressed, as it can be incorporated in the verb itself. Even when a subject is incorporated in the verb, it is still considered a sentence constituent. Regarding the obligatoriness or optionality of sentence constituents, the verb and the subject (or Agent) in verbal sentences, as well as the *mubtada'* and *ḥabar* in nominal sentences, are obligatory sentence parts (cf. Ziegler 2017: 30). Similar to German, a subject is inquired using question words like *man?* (who?) or *māsa?* (what?) and is anaphorized with *aḥadun/šai'un* (someone/something) or personal pronouns in the nominative case such as *huwa* (he), *hiya* (she), etc. In Arabic, there is no neutral personal pronoun for "it", only masculine and feminine forms.

The subject complement can also appear in the form of an infinitive clause introduced by the particle *an* (that), e.g.

Arab. *yakfī an (bi-an) tunğisa ḥāsā l- 'amala bi-mufradika*

Literal: "It is enough that you accomplish this work by yourself."

English: "It is enough that you accomplish this work alone."

The Arabic passive form is often formed by changing the vowelization of a verb. If the subject of the active sentence is mentioned in the passive sentence, a passive construction is used, which consists of the verb *tamma* (meaning "to happen, fulfill, take place," etc.) and the verbal noun of the verb from the active sentence. The subject of the active sentence is referred to in this passive construction with a prepositional phrase marked with *ğarr* (genitive). Possible prepositions include *min* (from) + genitive or *'an tarīqi* (by means of), e.g.

Arab. *tamma ḍarbu r-ruğuli min aḥadi l-muhāğimīna*

Literal: "The strike of the man was fulfilled by an attacker."

English: "The man was struck by an attacker."

Comparison

The "subject complement" of E-VALBU corresponds to the Arabic *fā'il* ("subject"). Both terms—"subject complement" and *fā'il*—are functionally similar in definition. In both German and Arabic, a subject complement is a sentence constituent in the nominative case that can appear as a noun, pronoun, or clause. Unlike some nominative-free verbs in German, all Arabic verbs require a nominative complement. An Arabic subject complement differs from a German one in that an Arabic subject can, in many cases, be incorporated into the verb itself. In contrast, a German subject always appears as an independent sentence constituent. In both languages, a subject complement is inquired by question words like *man?* (who?) and anaphorized with *aḥadun/sai'un* (someone/something) or personal pronouns in the nominative case such as *huwa* (he), etc.

5.1.2. Accusative Complement (Kakk)

According to VALBU, the accusative complement is a sentence constituent in the accusative case that refers to the object of the action. This complement of a full verb is inquired with *wen?* (whom?) or *was?* (what?) and is anaphorized with *jemanden/etwas* (someone/something) or personal pronouns in the accusative case (ihn/sie/es), e.g., *Sie liebt diesen Mann.* (She loves this man.)

Ihre Hilfe wird er annehmen müssen. (He will have to accept her help.)

In a sentence with a *werden* or *sein* passive construction, the accusative complement of the active sentence is realized as a nominal phrase or a pronominal phrase in the nominative case. Active sentence: *Sie liebt diesen Mann.* (She loves this man.)

Passive sentence: *Dieser Mann wird von ihr geliebt.* (This man will be loved by her.)

A sentence-like accusative complement (SKakk) is an accusative complement realized as a subordinate clause. Sentence-like accusative complements can be used with a correlate when they follow the main clause, e.g.,

Das Gericht hatte es abgelehnt, dass neben ihnen ihr Anwalt als Zuhörer Platz nehmen durfte. (The court had rejected that their lawyer could sit as a listener next to them.)

(Reference: E-VALBU Accusative Complement)

Some phrases in the accusative are not considered accusative complements:

- The internal object of a full verb, which is not otherwise connected to any accusative complement, such as in the verb *gehen* (to go): *Er geht einen schweren Gang* (He walks a heavy step). The internal object is classified as a supplement or specification in both E-VALBU and VALBU.
- The *Erstreckungsakkusativ* (extent accusative), i.e., the phrase answering questions like "How long?", "How wide?", "How high?", "How heavy?", etc., is classified as a dilative adverbial complement of quantity (Kadv), e.g.,
Die Sitzung hat einen ganzen Tag gedauert. (The meeting lasted a whole day.)
- The phrase in the accusative answering the question "How?" is classified as a predicative complement (Kpraed), e.g.,
Man nannte ihn einen Idioten. (They called him an idiot.)
- The *Pertinenzakkusativ* (pertinence accusative) is not considered a complement in E-VALBU and VALBU. For example, in *Peter hat mich ans Schienbein getreten* (Peter kicked me in the shin), it is not counted as a complement.

The Arabic term *maf'ūlun bihi* (مفعول به) "accusative object" is understood as the sentence element with which something happens. For example:

Arab. yahtarimu n-nāsu l-'ulamā'a – literally, "The people respect the scholars."

Dt. Die Menschen respektieren die Gelehrten. (The people respect the scholars.)

The Arabic accusative object refers to "the object of a verbal sentence, or better yet, the patient object, and thus the entity affected by the action expressed by the verb" (El-Fakharany 1989: 92, cf. Hasan 1961: 125). This object appears with a *fatha* (naṣb) marking, provided it consists of a single word that does not end with *a*.

The Arabic *maf'ūlun bihi* (accusative object) has different forms of expression. It can appear as a nominal phrase (*Arab. Khalid yaktubu ḥiṭāban* – "Khalid writes a letter"), a pronominal phrase in the accusative (*Arab. Khalid yaktubuhu* – "Khalid writes it"), or a subordinate clause, either with an *anna*-clause or *an* + subjunctive (*arāda an yabqa aḥūhu ladaihi* – "He wanted his brother to stay with him") (Hammam 1994: 199).

The accusative object, along with all other objects, is interpreted by nearly all Arabic grammarians as an optional adjunct (*faḍl*). Only Ibn as-Sarrāḡ acknowledges the semantic necessity of a *maf'ūl* ("object") (cf. Ziegler 2017: 30). The accusative object is queried with the question words *man?* (who?) or *mā?* (what?) and is anaphorized with *aḥadun mā* (someone), *šai'un mā* (something), or with a personal pronoun in the accusative, such as *~hu / ~ha* (him/her), for example:

Arab. taqra'u r-riwāyata / taqra'uha

– "She reads the novel / it."

Dt. Sie liest den Roman / ihn.

It is noteworthy that the Arabic question word *man?* (who?) remains unchanged in both the accusative and nominative, while the German *wer?* (who?) changes to *wen?* (whom?) in the accusative.

In a passive sentence, the accusative object from the active sentence is realized as a nominative nominal phrase or pronominal phrase. For example:

Aktivsatz: Arab. ahāna l-'āmila – literally "He insulted the worker."

Dt. Er beleidigte den Arbeiter.

Passivsatz: Arab. uhīna l-'āmilu – literally "The worker was insulted."

Dt. Der Arbeiter wurde beleidigt.

In addition to the function described above as the accusative object, there are other functions in Arabic that are fulfilled by accusative constituents. Msellek's work (1988: 62–71) did not fully address all the functions of the accusative in Arabic. According to Taha (2008: 175ff.), Ibn as-Sarrāġ distinguished between eight different types of objects, but later studies identify up to fifteen accusatives. Nevertheless, it can be stated that the most important accusatives are the following six types:

I. *almaf'ūl fīhi* "Accusative of Time or Place"

The *almaf'ūl fīhi* determines the local and temporal circumstances of an event, thus corresponding to a local and temporal adverbial complement. Further details can be found below under section (f).

II. *almaf'ūl li-'ajlihi* "Accusative of Purpose" (Kakk/purpose)

This Arabic object refers to the reason through which an event occurs and indicates a relationship between cause and effect. This object, which is in the accusative, is expressed in German through an adverbial complement labeled "purpose" (*Kadv/zweck*). While the forms of expression in both languages diverge syntactically, there is a semantic similarity in their functional perspective. For example:

Arab. hāġara ilā l-gharbi ta'alluman – literally, "He emigrated to the West for further education."

Dt. Er wanderte in den Okzident aus, um sich weiterzubilden.

III. *almaf'ūl ma'ahu* "Accusative with 'and'" (Kakk/waw)

In this object, which is in the accusative, it is indicated how something or someone is part of an action. It is marked by the particle *wa* (and). The particle *wa*, which formally appears as a conjunction, should here not be interpreted as a conjunction but rather as a preposition corresponding to the preposition *mit* in German. For example:

Arab. sāfara wa samīlaha – literally, "He traveled and his colleague."

Dt. Er fuhr mit seinem Kollegen.

In German, *almaf'ūl ma'ahu* is predominantly expressed through a modal adverbial complement (*Kadv/modal*). Here, there is a significant structural difference between Arabic and German, while the functional purpose remains similar.

IV. *almaf'ūl al-muṭlaq* "Inner Object" (Kakk/inner)

The Arabic "Inner Object" enhances the meaning of a sentence. It is usually accompanied by an adjectival modifier and also serves an adverbial function. *almaf'ūl al-muṭlaq* corresponds to the "inner object" in German (*Kinner*), so there is both a formal and semantic similarity between the two languages. In line with German, the inner object is in the accusative, but this object is not considered a complement in *VALBU*, for example:

Arab. taqāṭalu qitālan šadīdan – literally, "They fought a fierce battle."

Dt. Sie kämpften einen heftigen Kampf gegen/mit einander.

V. *at-tamyyes* "Accusative of Specification" (Kakk/spez)

The *at-tamyyes* is an indeterminate accusative that serves to clarify a preceding word or phrase, often related to weight, measurement, quantity, or amount. In German, *at-tamyyes* is often expressed through an adverbial complement with the label "amount" or "dilative" (*Kadv/menge*). For example:

Arab. yasinu r-raġulu smānīna keelo ġirāman – literally, "The man weighs 80 kg."

Dt. Der Mann wiegt 80 Kg.

VI. *al-ḥāl* "Accusative of State" (Kakk/zustand)

The Arabic *al-ḥāl* refers to a state that occurs simultaneously with the action described by the verb. It is one of the nominal forms in the indeterminate accusative, marked with the suffix *-an* (which is a nunation, and sometimes with the letter *alif* with a *fathatan* at the end). The

accusative of state often corresponds to a synthetic sentence. For example:
Arab. qāmat `ilayhi bākiyatan – literally, "She approached him weeping" (cf. Fischer 1987: 173f.).

Dt. Sie trat zu ihm weinend.

In German, the Arabic *al-ḥāl* "accusative of state" is often expressed through an adverbial complement indicating "manner" (*Kadv/art/weise*). This *al-ḥāl* appears with both transitive and intransitive verbs, for example:

Arab. atā l-ibnu dāhikan – literally, "The son came laughing."

Dt. Der Sohn kam lächelnd.

Additionally, there are other accusatives that are less commonly used than the previous ones, including:

a. **al-istitnā' (Exception Accusative)**: This refers to the exception with the preposition *illā* (except) in positive statements. For example:

Abu Chacra (2017: 355).

b. **an-nidā' (Vocative Accusative)**: This refers to the accusative used in the vocative case when more than one noun is dependent on *yā* (O). For example:

(cf. *Al-Rawaschdeh 2007: 166*).

c. **The Object of *kān* in the Nominal Sentence**: This refers to the accusative of the object in a nominal sentence where *kān* (was) is used. For example:

(cf. *Al-Rawaschdeh 2007: 166*).

d. **The Subject of *in* (If)**: This refers to the accusative used when *in* (if) is used in sentences. For example:

(cf. *Al-Rawaschdeh 2007: 166*).

e. **an-nafy bi-lā (Accusative of General Negation)**: This refers to the accusative used for general negation, often expressed with the particle *lā* (no) for negation.

As a consequence, the previous functions are still regarded as accusative complements or as different forms of the accusative that are more similar to the functions of German adverbial complements. Therefore, in the complement class table presented below, they are listed on the Arabic side as subcategories of the accusative object, such as "accusative of the cause," "accusative of the instrument," etc.

Comparison

In both German and Arabic, an accusative complement is interpreted as a syntactic element in the accusative case associated with a transitive verb. This interpretation holds for Arabic when discussing an Arabic verbal sentence. In both languages, an accusative complement appears in various forms, such as a nominal or pronominal phrase in the accusative or a subordinate clause. In terms of the property of anaphorization, there is functional identity between German and Arabic. In both languages, an accusative object is queried with question words such as *man?* (who?), and it is anaphorized using certain expressions like personal pronouns in the accusative case.

In Arabic, an accusative complement also serves other functions beyond being the object of an action. These functions are frequently fulfilled in German by adverbial complements. The different functions of the Arabic accusative complement are highlighted through an expansion of terminology: *accusative of the cause*, *accusative of the state*, etc. Additionally, German has certain special phrases in the accusative that are not considered accusative complements.

An Arabic accusative complement is not only rendered in German by an accusative complement but also by other equivalent forms, such as a dative, genitive, or prepositional complement.

5.1.3. Dative Complement (Kdat)

A dative complement of a full verb (Kdat) is a phrase in the dative case that provides additional information about an action. This dative complement is queried with the question *whom?* and anaphorized with expressions such as *someone*, *something*, or personal pronouns in the dative (*him*, *her*, *them*). Examples:

- *I couldn't always follow his words.*
- *Paul gave me a book.*

In a sentence with a *bekommen* passive, the dative complement of the active sentence is realized as a noun phrase in the nominative:

- **Active sentence:** *Someone gave him a book.*
- **Bekommen-passive:** *He receives a book.*

However, some dative phrases are not considered as complements:

a. **Dativus ethicus:** This expresses emotional involvement. Example: *You are a hypocrite to me!*

b. **Dativus iudicantis:** This indicates from whose perspective something is being asserted. Example: *That's too little for me.*

c. **Dativus commodi/incommodi:** This expresses who benefits or is disadvantaged by an action. Example: *He bought his sister a tennis racket. / They cut our Christmas bonus.*

d. **Pertinenzdativ:** This expresses possession. Example: *Wash your hair!*

Overall, the dative complement is often queried with *whom?* and plays an important role in identifying the recipient or beneficiary of an action.

In Arabic, there is no dative case. The person or object that is affected by an action or event (e.g., *uhdika/uhdi ilaika kitaban* – literally "I gift you a book" or "I gift for you a book") is referred to using an accusative or a prepositional phrase with *garr* marking (genitive). The German dative complement is expressed in Arabic either through a *la*-phrase, an accusative, or a prepositional complement with *ǧarr* marking (genitive), as in the example *ahdā l-mudarrisu t-tilmīsa/ilā t-tilmīsi kitāban* – literally "The teacher gifted the student/ to the student's a book" (in German: "The teacher gave the student a book").

The rules mentioned in point (b) regarding the questioning with *man?* (who?) or *mā?* (what?), the anaphorization with *aḥadun mā* (someone), *šai'un mā* (something), or with personal pronouns in the accusative *-hu / -ha* (him/her), and the passive construction also apply here.

Comparison

In contrast to German, Arabic does not have a dative complement because Arabic lacks verbs that govern the dative case in sentences. While in German, the dative complement appears as

a purely case-marked verb complement, in Arabic, it appears either as a *la*-phrase, an accusative, or as a prepositional complement with *ğarr* marking.

5.1.4. Genitive Complement (Kgen)

According to VALBU, the genitive complement is a phrase or constituent that functions as the genitive object of a full verb. A genitive complement is queried with *whose?* and is anaphorized with *someone's/something's* or personal pronouns in the genitive (whose, his, hers, etc.), for example: *He assured the president of his friendship*. A genitive phrase that answers the question "how" is considered a predicative complement: *He was in good spirits*. A genitive complement can also take the form of a subordinate clause (SKgen), for example: *Can you remember whether we received the invitation from Dr. Kunz?* Sentence-like genitive complements are rare in current usage, but they can be used with a correlate. (See: [Genitive Complement](#) and Genitive Clause Complement).

In Arabic, there is no genitive complement. The German genitive complement is either rendered in Arabic by an accusative complement (e.g., *yatasakkaru š-š'bu daḥāyā l-ḥarb* — *The people remember the victims of the war*) or by a prepositional complement with *ğarr*-marking (genitive marking) (e.g., *yattahimu l-būlisu l-ğāra bi-l-qatli* — *The police suspect the neighbor of murder*). The rules mentioned in point b, which involve querying with *man?* (who?) or *māsa?* (what?), anaphorization with *aḥadun mā* (someone), *šai'un mā* (something), or personal pronouns in the accusative (*-hu / -ha*), and passive constructions, also apply here.

Comparison

Unlike in German, Arabic has no genitive complement, since Arabic does not have verbs that require the genitive. A German genitive complement is either represented in Arabic as an accusative complement or as a prepositional complement with *ğarr*-marking.

5.1.5. Prepositional Complement (Kprp/gen)

In German, the prepositional complement of a full verb is a phrase (sentence element) that is introduced by a preposition. The prepositional complement is characterized by one, two, or occasionally three fixed prepositions for a verb or reading of a verb: *Die Opposition stimmt für/gegen das Gesetz* (The opposition votes for/against the law). The prepositional complement is queried with a preposition + who (to whom? about whom? from whom? ...) or where + preposition (where to? about what? from what?...). This complement is anaphorized with a preposition + someone / personal pronoun or prepositional adverb (to someone, to him, from her, on it, for it, from it...), e.g., *Ich denke an dich* (I think of you). *Das liegt an dir* (That's up to you). *Er hält nichts von diesem Vorschlag* (He thinks nothing of this suggestion).

Adverbial complements that are also realized in the form of a prepositional phrase are, however, anaphorized by adverbs (see Kadv). A prepositional complement can also appear as a sentence-like prepositional complement (SKprp). Sentence-like prepositional complements can be used with a correlate, e.g., *Der Wohlstand des Landes hängt davon ab, dass es die Ressourcen möglichst produktiv einsetzt* (The prosperity of the country depends on it using its resources as productively as possible). (See hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de and hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de).

In Arabic, the so-called *almaf'ūl bi-ḥarf* (prepositional object) is a prepositional phrase whose nominal core is in the genitive. The preposition is not interchangeable, e.g., (*Arab.*) *tahtammu d-daulatu bi s-sirā'ati* (The state is concerned with agriculture). This is equivalent to the German prepositional complement (Kprp), meaning both terms in the respective languages are almost identical. All Arabic prepositions consistently require the genitive, so a

prepositional object always has a *ğarr*-marking (genitive marking), e.g., (*Arab.*) *tantabihu l-ummu ilā ṭiflihā* (The mother pays attention to her child). An Arabic prepositional object can also appear with different fixed prepositions, just like in German.

The Arabic prepositional object is queried with the preposition dependent on the verb, e.g., 'an (about) + the question word *man?* (who?). The preposition 'an (about) and the question word *man?* are merged into the question word 'amma*n?* (about whom?). When the question refers to a thing, the prepositional object is queried with the preposition 'an (about) + *ma?* (what?), with two synonymous question words appearing: 'amma or 'an ai šai'in? (about what?).

The Arabic prepositional object is anaphorized through: a) Preposition + pronoun phrase, e.g., (*Arab.*) *Yahtammu bihi* (He is concerned with him), (*German.*) *Er beschäftigt sich mit ihm*. b) An infinitival clause or complement clause initiated by the particle *an* (that), e.g., (*Arab.*) *kāna ya'malu an asūruhu* (He hoped that I would visit him), (*German.*) *Er hoffte darauf, dass ich ihn besuche*.

In Arabic, the following prepositions appear in prepositional complements: *bi* (with), *li* (to), *min* (from), 'an (about), *ma'a* (with), *fī* (in), and 'ala (on).

Comparison

In Arabic, the concept of a prepositional object aligns with its equivalent in German. In both languages, a prepositional object is a prepositional phrase that is associated with a restrictively interchangeable preposition. In both languages, different fixed prepositions can occur with a prepositional object. The distinction lies in that, while in German the prepositions govern various cases, in Arabic they always govern the genitive. An Arabic prepositional object always carries a *ğarr*-marking (genitive marking). In German, an Arabic prepositional object is either represented by a prepositional object or by an accusative object. In both languages, a prepositional object is queried with the respective prepositions and anaphorized with specific constructions such as: preposition + noun/pronoun or prepositional adverb.

5.2. Adverbial Complement (Kadv)

In German, there are not only local and temporal adverbial complements, as in Arabic, but also other types of adverbial classes. An adverbial complement (Kadv) is a phrase (sentence constituent) that is realized either as an adverb or as a prepositional phrase and depends on the full verb as a circumstantial modifier, for example: "Ich wohne dort" (I live there), "Ich wohne in Mannheim" (I live in Mannheim). The detailed elaboration of the different adverbial complements happens one level deeper within the system (see Kubczak 2013: 59f.). Adverbial complements are subclassified according to their different meanings, such as location (static), location (directive), time, quantity, manner, means/instrument, purpose, and connection. The adverbial complement is questioned with: wo? wohin? wann? wie lange? wie viel? wie? womit? wozu? wobei?

In the case of an adverbial complement, the anaphor is always an adverbial pronoun: irgendwo/dort (somewhere/there), irgendwann/dann (sometime/then), irgendwohin/dorthin (somewhere to/there), irgendwie (somehow), mittels irgendetwas (with something), irgendwozu (for something), irgendwobei (while doing something), for example: "Das Inhaltsverzeichnis steht am Anfang des Buchs" (The table of contents is at the beginning of the book), "Sie fährt nach Heidelberg" (She is going to Heidelberg), "Die Sitzung beginnt um drei Uhr" (The meeting starts at three o'clock). An adverbial complement can also be realized in the form of a clause (SKadv), for example: "In der ganzen Welt amüsieren sich

Zoobesucher dabei, Affen von Ast zu Ast springen zu sehen" (All over the world, zoo visitors enjoy seeing monkeys jump from branch to branch). Clausal adverbial complements are rare and are used with an obligatory correlate (see Kubczak 2011: 115f., also <http://hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de/evalbu/Begrifflichkeiten/Adverbativkomplement.html>).

The Arabic term **al-maf'ūlu fihī** (المفعولُ فيه) refers to an adverbial phrase that is realized in different forms. It is an accusative object that expresses a fact or event in terms of its local or temporal context. In comparison with German, it corresponds to the local and temporal adverbial complements, which is why the term "local and temporal adverbial complements" is used for both languages.

Although **al-maf'ūlu fihī** and its German counterpart agree in terms of the temporality and locality of an event, there is a syntactic difference: In Arabic, it is in the accusative, as shown in the example:

- Arabic: **yusāfiru l-wafdu muta'hiran** (Literal: "The delegation travels late").
- German: "The delegation travels late."

In Arabic, the term **muta'hiran** (late) is considered an accusative adverb, which is not the case in German.

In Arabic, there are two types of local adverbial complements: situational and directive adverbial determinations. Both types occur either as accusative adverbs or in the form of a prepositional construction with a genitive marking. These local and temporal adverbial complements in Arabic differ from German due to the differing case rules. While in German a preposition in situational and directive complements can govern the accusative, dative, or genitive, in Arabic, a preposition always requires the genitive. For example:

- Arabic: **tashabu l-'āna ilā l-madrasati** (Literal: "She goes now to the school").
- German: "She goes now to the school."

In Arabic, there are also verbs that, in addition to a local prepositional complement, express local/directive information through an accusative complement. For example:

- Arabic: **waṣalat ṭ-ṭa'iratu ilā l-maṭāri** (Literal: "The plane arrived at the airport").
- German: "The plane arrived at the airport."
- Arabic: **waṣalat ṭ-ṭa'iratu l-maṭāra** (Literal: "The plane arrived the airport").
- German: "The plane arrived the airport."

A temporal adverbial complement in Arabic can express both a punctual meaning and a durative meaning:

- Punctual: **ya'ti l-qitāru l-'āna** (Literal: "The train comes now").
- Durative: **yastamirru d-darsu sā'atan** (Literal: "The lesson lasts one hour").
- German: "The lesson lasts one hour."

There are also adverbs in Arabic that express a conditional relationship and are in the accusative. After such adverbs, a noun that requires a genitive marking always follows. For example:

- Arabic: **'inda taḥassuni ṣiḥḥatihi sa-yughādiru l-mustašfā** (Literal: "At the improvement of his health, he will leave the hospital").

- German: "At the improvement of his health, he will leave the hospital."

The Arabic adverb 'inda performs the same conditional function as the Arabic 'indama, which requires two clauses (main and subordinate). The sentence could also be expressed as:

- Arabic: 'indama tataḥassun ṣiḥḥatahu sa-yuḡhādiru l-mustašfā (Literal: "When his health improves, he will leave the hospital").
- German: "When his health improves, he will leave the hospital."

These differences in syntactic structure and case usage between Arabic and German highlight the complexity of adverbial expressions in both languages.

The local Arabic adverbial complement is queried with **aina?** (where?), **ilā aina?** (where to?), and the temporal adverbial complement with **matā?** (when?), **kam mina l-waḡti?** (for how long?), as shown in the examples:

- Arabic: **aina yaskunu?** (Literal: "Where lives?")
German: "Where does he live?" → Arabic: **yaskunu fi l-qaryati** (Literal: "Lives in the village.")
German: "He lives in the village."

The Arabic adverbial complement with a local meaning can be anaphorized with **hunā** (here), **hunāka** (there), and with a directive meaning through **ilā makānin mā/ilā hunāk** (somewhere/to there), **fi makānin mā** (somewhere). The temporal adverbial complement is anaphorized with **alān** (now), **fi hasā l-waḡti** (at that time), **fi waḡtin mā/ba'da sālik** (sometime/then), **ṭawīlan mina l-waḡti** (for so long), as shown in the examples:

- Arabic: **istammarat l-ḡalsatu arba' a sā' ātin** (Literal: "Lasted the meeting 4 hours.")
German: "The meeting lasted 4 hours." → Arabic: **Kam istammarat l-ḡalsatu?**
German: "How long did the meeting last?" → Arabic: **istammarat l-ḡalsatu tawīlan** (Literal: "Lasted the meeting long.")
German: "The meeting lasted so long."

The construction **4 Stunden**, which in German is considered a dilative complement, is represented in Arabic by specification in the accusative (**arba' u sā' ātin**). Apart from the aforementioned forms of the Arabic local complement (as a prepositional phrase and as an adverb), it can also appear as a subordinate clause, as in:

- Arabic: **ta' i šu hai tu ya' išu sawḡuha** (Literal: "Lives where lives husband her.")
German: "She lives where her husband lives."

Comparison

In both German and Arabic, an adverbial complement is semantically defined in the same way. It is a phrase with an adverbial meaning realized in various forms. An Arabic adverbial complement differs from a German adverbial complement in that it is in the accusative case. In both languages, an adverbial complement describes a fact or event in terms of its local and temporal relationships. In line with German, Arabic has spatial or local adverbial complements with situational and directive meanings, as well as temporal adverbial complements with punctual and durative meanings.

The other German classes of adverbial complements, which include purpose, quantity, manner, etc., exist in Arabic under additional forms in the accusative, such as the accusative

of reason, specification word in the accusative, and accusative of state. In both languages, there are adverbs that refer to the entire sentence:

- Arabic: **ghadan sawfa āti** (Literal: "Tomorrow will come.")
German: "Tomorrow I will come."

However, these adverbs are not complements, as they are not dependent on the verb. The preposition that occurs in an adverbial complement, unlike the preposition in a prepositional object, is not fixed and interchangeable. The prepositions in Arabic adverbial complements differ from German due to the different case systems. Both the German and Arabic adverbial complements are queried with specific question words like **where?** (**aina?**) and anaphorized with adverbs like **here** (**hunā**), **there** (**hunāka**), and others.

5.3. Predicative Complement (Kprd)

In German, a predicative complement (Kprd) is a phrase (sentence constituent) that depends on a copular verb and denotes an attribute, state, or similar quality of the subject or object of the copular verb. The predicative complement is queried with "how?" (wie?) or "what?" (was?). It is anaphorized with words like "so," "such a," "as such," "therefore," etc. For example:

- *Das Wetter ist schön* ("The weather is beautiful").
- *Mein Vater ist Arzt* ("My father is a doctor").
- *Man nannte ihn einen Idioten* ("They called him an idiot").
- *Sie gilt als originell* ("She is considered original").
- *Wir hielten ihn für dumm* ("We thought he was dumb").

In addition to the typical copular verbs **sein** (to be), **werden** (to become), and **bleiben** (to remain), other verbs or verb readings such as **gelten** (to be considered), **scheinen** (to seem), **nennen** (to name), **halten für** (to consider), and **sich fühlen** (to feel) are also classified as copula verbs. For example:

- *Sie gilt als kompetent* ("She is considered competent").
- *Er scheint reich* ("He seems rich").
- *Man nannte ihn einen Idioten* ("They called him an idiot").
- *Man hält ihn für dumm* ("They consider him dumb").
- *Sie fühlt sich wie eine Königin* ("She feels like a queen").

A predicative noun or pronoun can be in the nominative or accusative case. It is in the accusative if its reference noun is in the accusative:

- *Man nannte den Mann einen Idioten* ("They called the man an idiot").
In this case, *den Mann* is the reference noun in the accusative, and *einen Idioten* is the predicative complement in the accusative.

Otherwise, the predicative complement is in the nominative:

- *Er war ein guter Lehrer* ("He was a good teacher").
- *Er wurde ein Idiot genannt* ("He was called an idiot").
- *Er gilt als ruhiger Mensch* ("He is considered a calm person").

The predicative complement has many forms, which are verb-dependent and will be listed for each possible interpretation of a verb.

Even though the term **khobar** is translated as "predicate" in German, predicative complements in both languages differ significantly. An Arabic predicative complement appears as a phrase or second constituent in a nominal sentence. A nominal sentence consists of a noun and a predicative complement. Unlike in German, an Arabic predicative complement does not require a copular verb.

An Arabic predicative complement appears in the following forms:

- **a. Verb:**
 - *allāgi `ūna yabkūna* (Literal: "The refugees weep").
German: "The refugees weep."
In this sentence, the predicative complement is the verb *yabkūna* itself.
- **b. Noun:**
 - *al`abu `ustāsun* (Literal: "The father professor").
German: "The father is a professor."
- **c. Adjective:**
 - *at-taqsu mustaqirr* (Literal: "The weather stable").
German: "The weather is stable."
- **d. Adverb:**
 - *al`usfūru hunāka* (Literal: "The sparrow there").
German: "The sparrow is there."
- **e. Adverbial with genitive marking:**
 - *al`usfūru fawqa š-šaġarati* (Literal: "The sparrow on the tree").
German: "The sparrow is on the tree."
- **f. Prepositional phrase with genitive marking:**
 - *alwafdu fī l-qaṣri* (Literal: "The delegation in the castle").
German: "The delegation is in the castle."

The words "there," "in the castle," etc., in the above sentences are considered predicative complements in Arabic. These cases differ from the adverbial complements mentioned earlier in that the former are parts of nominal sentences (sentences without a verb), whereas the latter are components of verbal sentences.

- **g. Verbal sentence:**
 - *addaulatu taḥtāġu da`man/ilā da`min* (Literal: "The state needs support/to support").
German: "The state needs support."
In the nominal sentence, the verb *taḥtāġu* ("needs") and its accusative or prepositional complement *da`man/ilā da`min* ("support/to support") act as the predicative complement.
- **h. Nominal sentence:**
 - *alqal`atu aswāruhā `āliyatun* (Literal: "The fortress, wall its high").
German: "The wall of the fortress is high."

Although some of the structures listed above consist of a preposition + genitive or an adverb, they are all classified as predicative complements in the nominative because they are used in nominal sentences.

An Arabic predicative complement is queried with **kaifa** (how?) or **māsa** (what?), and it is anaphorized with expressions like **hakasā** (so), **mitlu sālika** (such a, such, such a one, as such), for example:

- *alḥaqibatu ghālijatum* (Literal: "The bag expensive").
German: "The bag is expensive."
→ How is the bag? → "The bag is so."

Comparison

In both German and Arabic, a predicative complement is a phrase or sentence constituent that characterizes a subject. An Arabic predicative complement appears as the second constituent in a nominal sentence and does not depend on a copular verb. Unlike in Arabic, in German a predicative complement can also refer to an object. The realization forms of the predicative complement differ somewhat between the two languages. For instance, the German sentence *Man nannte ihn einen Idioten* ("They called him an idiot") includes "einen Idioten" as a predicative complement, whereas its Arabic equivalent *usammīhi maġnūnan* ("I call him an idiot") treats "maġnūnan" as a second accusative object.

Both German and Arabic predicative complements are queried with question words like **how?** (**kaifa?**) and are anaphorized with expressions like **so** (**hakasā**), among others.

5.4. Verbatum Complement (Kvrb)

A verbatim complement is the complement of a full verb in the form of an infinitive clause or a "that"-clause. The Kvrb cannot be replaced by a nominal or pronominal phrase, which distinguishes it from other sentence-level realizations of complements from other classes. For example: "He forbade her any exit" [Kakk], "He forbade her to leave" [sentence-level realization of a Kakk], "He motioned for me to sit down" [Kvrb]. In this case, "to sit down" cannot be replaced by a noun phrase, so it is a verbatim complement. This complement is often anaphorized with expressions like "to do something," "that it is so," or "that it happens," such as "The medication begins to take effect" or "The subjects believe that the taxes must be reduced" (see <http://hypermedia.ids-mannheim.de/evalbu/begriffe.html>).

For Arabic: An Arabic verb complement is a secondary verb that complements the meaning of a main verb and appears in the form of a finite verb or an infinitive clause introduced by the particle "an" (to). There are only a few verbs in Arabic that can connect with a verb complement:

a. **kāda**, **karaba**, **awšaka** (meaning "to be close to doing something"), b. **ʿasā**, **ḥarā**, **iḥlāulaqa** (meaning "it might be that..."), c. **šāra**, **ġaʿala**, **aḥasa**, **ṭafiqa** (meaning "to become, to begin doing something"), d. **taraka** (meaning "to leave").

Most of these verbs—**karaba**, **ʿasā**, **ḥarā**, **iḥlāulaqa**, and **ṭafiqa**—are always in the past tense, never in the present. The remaining verbs—**kāda**, **awšaka**, **šāra**, **ġaʿala**, **aḥasa**, and **taraka**—appear in both tenses:

- In the present tense (e.g., **baʿda qalīlīn yašbaḥu l-muʿallimu mudīran** meaning "Soon the teacher will become the principal."),
- In the past tense (e.g., **ašbaḥa l-maʿdanu sahaban** meaning "The metal became gold.").

Additionally, the verbs **kāda**, **awšaka**, **šāra**, **ġaʿala**, **aḥasa**, and **taraka** can be used as either main or secondary verbs. When used as secondary verbs in the past tense, they require either a verb complement (e.g., **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu yašruḥu** meaning "The child began to cry"), a prepositional verbal noun with genitive marking (e.g., **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu fi ṣ-ṣurāḥi** meaning "The child began in crying"), or an infinitive clause with "an" (e.g., **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu fi an yašruḥ** meaning "The child began to cry").

When used as full verbs, they take on different meanings and can appear in both the present and past tense (e.g., **ya'ḥusu/aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu l-li' bata** meaning "The child takes/ took the toy").

The Arabic verb complement can be replaced by a nominal phrase (e.g., **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu yaşruḥu** meaning "The child began crying" → **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu fi ş-şurāhi** meaning "The child began in crying"), and it can be anaphorized similarly using **hakasā/sālik/fi sālik** (meaning "to do something") (e.g., **aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu fi sālik** meaning "The child began so doing").

Comparison

In both German and Arabic, a verb complement can be defined as a secondary verb that serves to complete the meaning of a main verb. The forms of this complement are not always identical in both languages. In German, a verb complement appears as an infinitive clause or a "that" clause. In Arabic, a verb complement appears in the form of a finite verb or an infinitive clause introduced by the particle "an" (that/to).

Unlike German, an Arabic verb complement can be replaced by a prepositional verbal noun with genitive marking or by an infinitive clause with "an" (that/to). In both languages, the verb complement is similarly anaphorized.

6. Tabular Presentation of German Verb Complements with Their Arabic Equivalents

6.1. Example Table Presentation

The following table includes the Arabic verb complements with their abbreviations, considering their equivalents in German. In accordance with the terminology of the VALBU valency model, the term "complement" is used instead of "Ergänzung" (supplement). The complement classes are illustrated through simple demonstration examples, making it easier and clearer for the reader to recognize the differences and similarities in sentence structures between Arabic and German.

When using the verb complement table presented below, the following note should be observed:

In the comparison table below, each Arabic verb complement and its corresponding German equivalent has a special number in square brackets [..] and an abbreviation. Arabic complement classes are referenced with digits, while German complement classes are referenced with letters. This numbering is used to determine the number of possible German equivalents for each Arabic verb complement individually.

□ Subject Complement (Ksub)

German: The child sleeps early.

Arabic: ينام الطفل باكراً

Translation: yanāmu al-ṭiflu bākiran

Word-for-word: The child sleeps early.

Equivalence degree: Identical

□ Accusative Complement (Kakk)

German: The girl reads a novel.

Arabic: تقرأ البنت رواية

Translation: taqrā'u al-bintu riwāyatan

Word-for-word: The girl reads a novel.

Equivalence degree: Identical

German: He defends his opinion.
Arabic: يدافع عن رأيه
Translation: yudāfi ‘u ‘an ra’yihi
Word-for-word: He defends his opinion.
Equivalence degree: Different

German: The state needs support.
Arabic: الدولة تحتاج دعماً/إلى دعم
Translation: ad-dawlatu tahtāju da‘man/ilā da‘min
Word-for-word: The state needs support / to support.
Equivalence degree: Different

□ **Genitive Complement (Kgen)**
German: The people commemorate the war victims.
Arabic: يتذكر الشعب ضحايا الحرب
Translation: yataḍakkaru ash-sha‘bu ḍaḥāyā al-ḥarbi
Word-for-word: The people remember the war victims.
Equivalence degree: Different

German: The police suspect the neighbor of murder.
Arabic: يتهم البوليس الجار بالقتل
Translation: yattahimu al-būlīs al-jāra bil-qatl
Word-for-word: The police suspect the neighbor with the murder.
Equivalence degree: Different

□ **Dative Complement (Kdat)**
German: The woman helps the refugees.
Arabic: تساعد المرأة اللاجئين
Translation: tusā‘idu al-mar’atu al-lāji‘īna
Word-for-word: The woman helps the refugees.
Equivalence degree: Different

German: The mother offers the daughter a gift.
Arabic: تقدم الأم لابنة هدية
Translation: tuqaddimu al-ummu li-l-ibnati hadiyyatan
Word-for-word: The mother offers the daughter a gift.
Equivalence degree: Different

□ **Prepositional Complement (Kpräp)**
German: The poor man asks for help.
Arabic: يطلب الفقير مساعدة
Translation: yaṭlubu al-faqīru musā‘datan
Word-for-word: The poor man asks for help.
Equivalence degree: Different

German: The state deals with agriculture.
Arabic: تهتم الدولة بالزراعة
Translation: tahtammu ad-dawlatu bil-zirā‘a
Word-for-word: The state cares about agriculture.
Equivalence degree: Almost identical

□ **Adverbial Complement (Kadv)**
German: The airplane is standing there.
Arabic: تقف الطائرة هناك

Translation: taqifu at-tā'iratu hunāka
Word-for-word: The airplane is standing there.
Equivalence degree: Identical

German: He lives in the village.
Arabic: يسكن في القرية
Translation: yaskunu fi al-qaryati
Word-for-word: He lives in the village.
Equivalence degree: Identical

□ **Accusative Complement of Specification (Kakk/spez)**

German: The man weighs 80 kilograms.
Arabic: يزن الرجل ثمانين كيلو جراما
Translation: yasinu ar-rajulu thamānīna kīlū ġirāman
Word-for-word: The man weighs 80 kilograms.
Equivalence degree: Identical

□ **Accusative Complement of Reason (Kakk/beweg)**

German: He killed him out of greed.
Arabic: قتله طمعا
Translation: qatalahu ṭama'an
Word-for-word: He killed him out of greed.
Equivalence degree: Identical

□ **Adverbial Complement of Condition (Kadv/kond/akk)**

German: When issuing the judgment, the judge must consider the mitigating circumstances.
Arabic: عند إصدار الحكم يجب على القاضي أن يراعي دواعي تخفيف العقوبة
Translation: 'inda iṣḍāri al-ḥukmi yajibu 'alā al-qāḍī an yurā'ī dawā'i taḥfīfi al-'uqūbati
Word-for-word: When issuing the judgment, the judge must consider the reasons for reducing the penalty.
Equivalence degree: Identical

7. Predicate Complement (Kpräd)

7.a. Predicate Complement (Kpräd)

German: The father is a professor.
Arabic: الأب أستاذ
Translation: al-'abu 'ustāsun
Word-for-word: The father professor.
Equivalence degree: Identical

7.b. Predicate Complement (Kpräd)

German: The weather is stable.
Arabic: الطقس مستقر
Translation: aṭ-ṭaqsu mustaqirrun
Word-for-word: The weather stable.
Equivalence degree: Identical

7.c. Predicate Complement (Kpräd)

German: They called him an idiot.
Arabic: سماه المرء مجنونا
Translation: sammahu l-mar'u magnunan
Word-for-word: Called him man an idiot.
Equivalence degree: Different

7.a. Predicate Complement in the form of a Noun (Kpräd/sub)

Arabic: الأب أستاذ

Translation: al-'abu 'ustāsun

Word-for-word: The father professor.

German: Der Vater ist Professor.

7.b. Predicate Complement in the form of an Adjective (Kpräd/adj)

Arabic: الطقس مستقر

Translation: aṭ-ṭaqsu mustaqirrun

Word-for-word: The weather stable.

German: Das Wetter ist beständig.

7.c. Accusative Complement (Kakk)

Arabic: سماه المرء مجنوناً

Translation: sammahu l-mar'u magnunan

Word-for-word: Called him man an idiot.

German: Man nannte ihn einen Idioten.

7.a. Identical

German: so be it

Arabic: هكذا

Translation: hakazā

Word-for-word: so be it

7.b. Identical

German: so be it

Arabic: هكذا

Translation: hakazā

Word-for-word: so be it

7.c. Different

German: so be it

Arabic: هكذا

Translation: hakazā

Word-for-word: so be it

8. Verbal Complement (Kverb)

German: The child began to cry.

Arabic: أخذ الطفل يصرخ

Translation: aḥasa ṭ-ṭiflu yaṣruḥu

Word-for-word: Began the child cry.

Equivalence degree: Partially identical

German: to do something

Arabic: يفعل شيئاً

Translation: yaf' alu šay'an

Word-for-word: Does something.

Equivalence degree: Partial

6.2. Condensed Tabular Representation

The following table provides a concise overview of all the previous verb complements in contrast.

German Complement Class	Arabic Equivalent
1. Subject Complement (Ksub)	Subject Complement (Ksub)
2. Accusative Complement (Kakk)	2.a. Accusative Complement (Kakk) 2.b. Prepositional Complement with ġarr-marking (Genitive) (Kpräp/gen) 2.c. Predicative Complement in the form of a Verbal Clause (Kpräd/vs)
3. Genitive Complement (Kgen)	3.a. Accusative Complement (Kakk) 3.b. Prepositional Complement with ġarr-marking (Genitive) (Kpräp/gen)
4. Dative Complement (Kdat)	4.a. Accusative Complement (Kakk) 4.b. Prepositional Complement with ġarr-marking (Genitive) (Kpräp/gen)
5. Prepositional Complement (Kpräp')	5.a. Accusative Complement (Kakk) 5.b. Prepositional Complement with ġarr-marking (Genitive) (Kpräp/gen)
6. Adverbial Complement (Kadv)	6.1. Adverbial Complement/Loc/Stat (Kadv/lok/stat) 6.2. Adverbial Complement/Loc/Direct (Kadv/lok/dirk) 6.3. Adverbial Complement/Temp/Point (Kadv/temp/punkt) 6.4. Adverbial Complement/Temp/Duration (Kadv/temp/dur) 6.5. Adverbial Complement/Means (Kadv/mittel) 6.6. Adverbial Complement/Modal or Manner (Kadv/art/weise) 6.7. Adverbial Complement/Quantity or Dilative (Kadv/menge) 6.8. Adverbial Complement/Purpose (Kadv/zweck) 6.9. Adverbial Complement/Context (Kadv/zusammenhang)

German Complement Class

Arabic Equivalent

- 6.1.a. Adverbial Complement/Loc/Stat/Acc
(Kadv/lok/stat/akk)
- 6.1.b. Prepositional Adverbial Complement with
ğarr-marking (Genitive)/Loc/Stat
(Kpräpadv/lok/stat/gen)
- 6.1.c. Predicative Complement in the form of an
Adverb in Accusative/Loc/Stat
(Kpräd/adv/lok/stat/akk)
- 6.1.d. Adverbial Predicative Complement in a
Genitive Construction/Loc/Stat
(Kpräd/adv/lok/stat/gen)
- 6.1.e. Predicative Complement in the form of a
Prepositional Phrase with ğarr-marking (Genitive)
(Kpräd/präpgr/gen)
- 6.2.a. Prepositional Adverbial
Complement/Loc/Direct with ğarr-marking
(Genitive) (Kpräpadv/lok/direk/gen)
- 6.2.b. Noun in the Accusative after waw (and)
(Kakk/waw)
- 6.3.a. Adverbial Complement/Temp/Point/Acc
(Kadv/temp/punkt/akk)
- 6.3.b. Adverbial Complement with ğarr-marking
(Genitive)/Temp/Point (Kadv/temp/punkt/gen)
- 6.3.c. Prepositional Adverbial Complement with
ğarr-marking (Genitive)/Temp/Point (Kpräp-
adv/temp/punkt/gen)
- 6.4.a. Adverbial Complement/Temp/Duration/Acc
(Kadv/temp/dur/akk)
- 6.4.b. Prepositional Adverbial Complement with
ğarr-marking (Gen)/Temp/Duration
(Kpräpadv/temp/dur/gen)
- 6.5.a. Prepositional Complement with ğarr-marking
(Genitive)/Means (Kpräp/mittel/gen)
- 6.5.b. Prepositional Noun of Instrument
(Kpräpinst/gen)
- 6.6. State Accusative (Kakk/zustand)
- 6.7. Accusative of Specification (Kakk/spez)
- 6.8. Accusative of Motivation (Kakk/beweg)
- 6.9. Adverbial Complement/Conditional Context/Acc
(Condition) (Kadv/kond/akk)
7. Predicative Complement (Kpräd)
- 7.a. Predicative Complement in the
form of a Noun (Kpräd/sub)
- 7.b. Predicative Complement in the
form of an Adjective (Kpräd/adj)
- 7.c. Accusative Complement (Kakk)
8. Verb Complement (Kverb)
8. Verb Complement (Kverb/finit)

7. Results and Solutions

When comparing the German complement classes with their Arabic equivalents, the presentation of the issues described above reveals discrepancies, various functional features, interesting differences, and some similarities between German and Arabic. Based on didactic and methodological concepts, specific difficulties that verb complements pose to Arabic-speaking German learners in practice can be addressed. As proposed solutions to overcome these problems, it is recommended that teachers follow the principle of hierarchy when teaching verb complements.

It has been found that applying the hierarchy in German language instruction plays a crucial role in mastering a foreign language. Initially, those verb complement classes that are almost identical to Arabic should be taught, such as nominative and accusative complements. Then, with sufficient demonstration examples, each German verb complement and its Arabic equivalent should be taught. Subsequently, a tabular presentation of all verb complement classes should be provided, allowing Arabic-speaking German learners to clearly understand the differences and similarities between the two languages.

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